

Design of Fuzzy Logic Controller for Inductor based Active Cell Balancing in the Battery Management System

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Abstract

Battery Management Systems are critical for ensuring the efficiency, reliability, and longevity of battery packs. Li-ion batteries are a proficient energy source for powering Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) due to their smaller size, lighter weight, and improved charge efficiency without the memory effect. The battery pack consists of a combination of cells in series and parallel configurations. The main problem is cell imbalance with inconsistent energy in the charging and discharging cycles of lithiumion batteries. To overcome this problem, a new multilayer equilibrium topology is designed in this paper, which utilizes active cell balancing using fuzzy logic to enhance battery life and efficiency. A fuzzy logic controller, namely FLC-TT with membership function shapes, is designed to divide the duty cycle of PWM switching signals. We performed modelling and simulation of the proposed system by MATLAB and Simulink software. The goal of this paper is to develop a system that can extend the lifespan of batteries by ensuring that each cell is charged and discharged evenly. The proposed system features an active balancing circuit that estimates the state of each battery cell and determines the optimal charging and discharging currents. The experiment shows that the cells with different states of charge get balanced to discharge through the load. This paper presents an automatic battery balancing circuit model utilizing a single-switch inductor with an SOC-based logic controller. The performances during static, charging, discharging, and mixed conditions are analyzed.

Keywords: *Li-Ion battery, active cell balancing, Fuzzy logic controller, State of Charge FLC-TT*